

D5.5 Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities (interim version)

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Editor(s)	Spyridoula Markou (ATC), George Triantafyllou (ATC)
Contributor(s)	Robert Seidl (Nokia), Oscar Garcia (i4RI), Bernd Ludwig Wenning (MTU), Francesca Giampaolo (ENG), Andrey Kuznetsov (WRCVE), Dmytro Prosvirin (ANTONOV), De Lutiis Paolo (TIM), Martin Gilje Jaatun (SINTEF), Steve Taylor (UoS), Dave Singelee (KUL), Sayon Duttagupta (KUL)
Reviewer(s)	Martin Gilje Jaatun (SINTEF), Francesca Giampaolo (ENG), Andrea Neverdal Skytterholm (SINTEF)
Document description	This document is the interim Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities, detailing the activities carried out up to Month 18. It also outlines the planned dissemination and communication efforts for the remainder of the project.

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This D5.5 “*Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities*” provides an overview of the dissemination and communication efforts undertaken during the first 18 months of the TELEMETRY project and outlines the future plans for the remainder of the project. As TELEMETRY reaches its midpoint, the dissemination strategy evolves to reflect the project’s progress, ensuring that outputs, tools, and methodologies are effectively communicated to the relevant target audiences.

Effective communication and dissemination are essential to ensuring that TELEMETRY’s findings reach the right stakeholders, foster collaboration, and enhance visibility within the cybersecurity and IoT security ecosystem. The dissemination process is a continuous effort throughout the project, adapting to new developments and refining strategies to maximise impact. TELEMETRY employs a multi-channel approach, leveraging scientific publications, the project website, social media, workshops, and participation in EU initiatives to ensure broad engagement. The project’s target audience includes Component Developers (CDs), System Integrators (SIs), System Operators (SOs), cybersecurity researchers, policymakers, regulators, and the general public, each of whom is addressed through tailored dissemination activities.

The dissemination and communication strategy follows a structured three-phase approach, each contributing to raising awareness and sustaining engagement throughout the project. Phase I – Inform & Connect (Months 1-36) focuses on establishing TELEMETRY’s identity, raising awareness, and engaging stakeholders through various digital and traditional communication channels, including the project website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and conference participation. As the project advances, Phase II – Demonstrate & Contribute (Months 18-36) shifts towards stakeholder engagement, showcasing initial results, and promoting the adoption of TELEMETRY’s solutions through workshops, clustering activities, and hands-on demonstrations. Finally, Phase III – Share & Convince (Months 30-36) builds upon previous efforts to ensure the long-term visibility and impact of TELEMETRY’s outcomes, reinforcing the project’s contributions beyond its duration. During the first 18 months, TELEMETRY has successfully established a strong communication infrastructure, including its website, social media presence, promotional materials, and participation in scientific and industry events. The project has also actively engaged in clustering activities from an initial stage, recognising the importance of proactive collaboration to foster long-term engagement and enable more targeted actions. Additionally, TELEMETRY has strengthened its connections with EU-wide initiatives, reinforcing its presence within the cybersecurity research and innovation landscape. These efforts have laid the foundation for the next phases, where more tools, methodologies, and research outputs will be finalised and actively disseminated.

Looking ahead, the next 18 months will focus on expanding dissemination efforts as additional project outputs become available. TELEMETRY will continue to enhance its communication channels, promote scientific publications and conference participation, and intensify engagement with key stakeholders. The LIFESEC workshop on 16th June and additional planned training sessions, demonstrations, and collaborative events will provide further opportunities to showcase the project’s results and maximise its impact.

By maintaining a flexible and adaptive dissemination strategy, TELEMETRY ensures that its findings, tools, and methodologies will continue to generate impact, foster collaboration, and contribute to a more secure and resilient IoT ecosystem across Europe. Through a continuous learning process, the project will refine its approach, messaging, and channels, ensuring maximum visibility and engagement within its target audiences.

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List of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ATC	Athens Technology Center
CDs	Component Developers
D5.1	Deliverable 5.1
D5.5	Deliverable 5.5
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures
ENG	Engineering
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EU	European Union
EUCC	European Union Cybersecurity Certification
i4RI	Data Analytics for Industries 4.0

IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
KUL	KU Leuven
LIFESEC workshop	Workshop on Whole-Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC)
MTU	Munster Technological University
NOKIA	Nokia Solutions and Networks GmbH & Co. KG
SIs	System Integrators
SOs	System Operators
TIM	Telecom Italia S.p.A.
UoS	University of Southampton
WG	Working Group
WP(s)	Work Package(s)
WRCVE	World Research Center Of Vortex Energy

1 Introduction

The TELEMETRY project is set to revolutionise the security landscape of IoT devices and systems. The project aims to develop and validate innovative and trustworthy tools and methods for testing and detecting security vulnerabilities in IoT environments. It will conduct three pilot programs in the telecoms, aerospace, and manufacturing sectors, ensuring broad applicability and impact. These pilots will showcase improvements in threat and vulnerability detection accuracy, response time, and the cost of testing and verification.

To ensure its long-term impact, TELEMETRY pursues four specific objectives:

- Developing holistic testing methodologies and integrating advanced tools into a comprehensive toolkit.
- Providing solutions for vulnerability detection and secure updates.
- Enhancing cyber threat intelligence and risk management.
- Grounding the project's innovations in real-world IoT ecosystems.

In this context, Work Package 5 (WP5) is responsible for the dissemination and communication of TELEMETRY's activities and results. The primary target audiences for these efforts include Component Developers (CDs), System Integrators (SIs), and System Operators (SOs), as these roles align with the IoT lifecycle. Other direct beneficiaries include cybersecurity researchers, the scientific community, and academia, who will benefit from TELEMETRY's publications and datasets. Additionally, policymakers and regulators represent indirect beneficiaries, as TELEMETRY's methodologies will support certification and compliance with EU standards, particularly within the European Union Cybersecurity Certification (EUCC) framework. Finally, the general public benefits indirectly through the development of more secure software and IoT devices used in everyday life.

To ensure effective outreach, a comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy (D5.1 "*Dissemination & Communication Plan*") was designed early in the project's lifecycle. Based on this strategy, TELEMETRY has conducted dissemination and communication activities over the first 18 months, leveraging both online and offline channels.

As outlined in D5.1, the strategy is structured into three progressive phases, spanning the project's three-year timeline. Each phase is tailored to achieve specific communication objectives (Figure 1). In detail:

- The first phase, **Inform & Connect** (Months 1-36), that runs throughout the project, focuses on establishing awareness and building the project's visibility. During this phase, TELEMETRY introduces its objectives, expected results, and relevance to key stakeholders. Dissemination efforts include the project website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and participation in conferences. Additionally, open-access

publications and clustering activities with other EU projects help strengthen collaboration and expand outreach.

- The second phase, **Demonstrate & Contribute** (Months 18-36), beginning in February 2025, will focus on promoting the project’s results and engaging target users. This phase will highlight intermediate findings, tool demonstrations, and use case developments to encourage stakeholder participation. Efforts will include scientific publications, participation in events and international conferences, and stronger collaborations with EU initiatives and funding programs to enhance TELEMETRY’s impact.
- The third phase, **Share & Convince** (Months 30-36), will aim to maximise the project’s long-term influence by leveraging its outcomes. Final results, key lessons, and industry applications will be widely shared through scientific journals, media coverage, and high-profile events.

Figure 1: The three phases of TELEMETRY dissemination and communication strategy

This deliverable, D5.5 “*Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities*”, serves as the first detailed report on the project’s dissemination and communication efforts. Its submission aligns with the midpoint of TELEMETRY’s lifecycle and falls within Phase I and the beginning of Phase II of the strategy.

During this period, dissemination and communication efforts have focused on two primary goals:

1. Establishing TELEMETRY’s presence and making the project known among its various target audiences. This included raising awareness among key stakeholders, industry players, researchers, and policymakers.
2. Strengthening engagement between different global communities of policymakers, industry experts, and practitioners, fostering collaborations that enhance the project’s impact.

Raising awareness was essential for generating interest in TELEMETRY’s objectives, methodologies, and expected outcomes. The first 18 months were dedicated to effectively communicating the project’s mission through multiple channels, including the project website, blog, X (formerly Twitter), and LinkedIn. These platforms allowed for broad dissemination, facilitating engagement with both technical and non-technical audiences. Additionally, participation in conferences, workshops, and networking events further extended TELEMETRY’s outreach, solidifying its position as a key player in IoT security and risk management.

1.1 Purpose and scope

This deliverable provides an overview of the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first 18 months of the TELEMETRY project, while also outlining the planned initiatives for the remainder of the project. It details the objectives and strategic approach followed during this reporting period, highlighting the tools and actions implemented to enhance the project’s visibility and outreach. Additionally, it presents the key activities undertaken to achieve the dissemination goals and aligns with the strategy established in Deliverable D5.1 “*Dissemination & Communication Plan*”.

1.2 Approach for Work Package and relation to other Work Packages and Deliverables

The activities and outcomes of WP5 “*Dissemination, Exploitation, and Outreach*”, particularly those under Task 5.1 “*Dissemination, Communications & Outreach*”, remain closely interconnected with the inputs received from all work packages, tasks, and deliverables within the TELEMETRY project. This deliverable builds upon the dissemination and communication

framework established in D5.1, incorporating contributions from all project partners to effectively communicate the results and progress of other WPs through WP5.

Key findings and major outcomes from each WP continue to be disseminated to a wider audience through participation in conferences and meetings, the project's website and social media channels (LinkedIn, X/Twitter and YouTube), as well as targeted outreach efforts and specific dissemination and communication templates. Additionally, every public deliverable of the project will be made accessible to external stakeholders via WP5 activities, ensuring broad dissemination through newsletters, press releases, and participation in events and conferences. The communication strategy leverages a mix of digital and offline channels to enhance visibility and engagement with the project's target audiences.

Given its cross-cutting role, WP5 remains highly dependent on the progress and outputs of all WPs and their corresponding deliverables, reinforcing its function in ensuring that TELEMETRY's results are effectively shared beyond the consortium, reaching the targeted audiences.

1.3 Methodology and structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is structured into six chapters, each providing a detailed account of the dissemination and communication efforts undertaken within the TELEMETRY project. In detail:

- Chapter 1 introduces the project, outlining its objectives and the role of WP5 in managing dissemination and communication activities. It also defines the purpose and scope of this deliverable.
- Chapter 2 provides a high-level summary of TELEMETRY's dissemination and communication strategy, along with an overview of planned activities.
- Chapter 3 focuses on the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first 18 months, covering the impact of the project website, engagement through social media channels, and both scientific and non-scientific dissemination efforts.
- Chapter 4 highlights the various dissemination materials developed to support outreach and visibility.
- Chapter 5 assesses the progress made by comparing the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as defined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and Deliverable D5.1, with the results achieved during the reporting period.
- Chapter 6 outlines the planned dissemination and communication activities for the remaining duration of the project, detailing future dissemination efforts, targeted events, and scientific publications that TELEMETRY aims to engage with.
- Finally, Chapter 7 provides a conclusion, summarising important takeaways from the report.
- The annexes include additional supporting materials related to the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first 18 months of the project.

2 Strategic Dissemination and Communication Plan at a glance

This chapter presents the dissemination and communication activities carried out so far in the first 18 months of the TELEMETRY project, as well as those planned for the next 18 months. It first outlines the actions implemented to date, assessing their impact and effectiveness in supporting the project's outreach objectives. It then provides an overview of the upcoming activities, highlighting how dissemination efforts will continue to evolve to maximise engagement and ensure long-term impact.

Following this, the chapter delves into a more detailed analysis of the strategic approach and key actions implemented across Year 1, Year 2, and Year 3, illustrating the project's progression from awareness-building to engagement and impact.

In the first 18 months, WP5 has concentrated on designing and executing a targeted strategy, ensuring the project's visibility and outreach at national, European, and international levels. These efforts have been carried out with the active participation of all project partners, who contribute to maximising the project's reach and engagement.

During this period, the primary Dissemination & Communication objectives were to:

- Establish and promote the TELEMETRY brand identity.
- Develop and distribute essential project materials.
- Communicate the project's vision and objectives to relevant audiences.
- Initiate stakeholder engagement and foster connections.
- Encourage the active involvement of various stakeholders.
- Extend outreach to a broader, non-expert audience.

2.1 Target audience, communication tools and expected impact

TELEMETRY is committed to making meaningful contributions by developing and validating advanced tools and methodologies for detecting and mitigating security vulnerabilities in IoT environments. The project is designed to address the needs of various stakeholder groups, ensuring that its findings and innovations effectively reach those who can benefit from them.

The **primary target audience** includes:

- Component Developers (CDs)
- System Integrators (SIs)
- System Operators (SOs)

The **secondary target group** includes:

- Cybersecurity researchers and the broader academic community
- Policymakers
- Regulators
- The general public

To effectively engage its diverse target groups, TELEMETRY employs tailored communication strategies and targeted outreach channels, ensuring that each audience receives relevant and impactful information. The table below (Table 1) outlines the specific tools used for dissemination and the intended impact for each target group.

Table 1: Approaching target groups

Target group	Tools	Intended Impact
Primary target audience		
Component Developers (CDs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Publications • Flyers • Workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of cybersecurity tools • Encourage adoption of TELEMETRY solutions • Support secure development practices
System Integrators (SIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Publications • Flyers • Multimedia Content (Videos, Infographics) • Workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote best practices for secure IoT systems • Ensure awareness of available tools • Foster collaboration in validation and adoption
System Operators (SOs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Multimedia Content (Videos, Infographics) • Publications • Podcasts • Workshops & Demonstrations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance cybersecurity implementation • Improve threat detection and response • Provide insights on vulnerability mitigation
Secondary target group		
Cybersecurity researchers & academic community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Publications (Scientific Journals, Conference Papers) • Podcasts • Social Media • Workshops & Conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate knowledge exchange • Encourage research collaboration • Provide access to new methodologies and datasets

Policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Publications • Flyers • Podcasts • Workshops & Conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of cybersecurity risks • Provide policy recommendations • Support informed decision-making
Regulators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Publications • Social Media • Multimedia Content • Podcasts • Workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform about compliance and standards • Encourage adoption of cybersecurity frameworks • Contribute to certification discussions
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media • Flyers • Podcasts • Multimedia Content (Videos, Infographics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase cybersecurity awareness • Promote digital safety best practices • Enhance understanding of secure infrastructures

2.2 Evolution of Dissemination and Communication: Year 1 to Year 3

The dissemination and communication strategy of the TELEMETRY project is designed to evolve over its three-year duration, aligning with the project's progress and key milestones. Phase I – Inform & Connect runs continuously throughout the project, ensuring ongoing awareness and engagement of the target groups. In Year 1, efforts focused on establishing visibility and laying the foundation for outreach. In Year 2, the focus shifted towards stakeholder engagement and collaboration, while continuing to communicate the project's developments. In the final year (Year 3), the strategy will emphasise the promotion of project outcomes, stakeholder adoption, and the long-term exploitation of TELEMETRY's results. As the project is currently on Month 18, this section outlines the dissemination activities carried out so far and provides an overview of those planned for the remainder of the project.

2.2.1 Year 1

During Year 1 of the TELEMETRY project (Figure 2), significant efforts were made to establish a strong communication and dissemination foundation. A comprehensive dissemination and communication plan (D5.1) was developed, outlining the project's strategy and outreach objectives. The official project website was launched, serving as a central hub for sharing key information, while social media accounts were created to enhance engagement with stakeholders and the wider public. To support visibility at events and online, a range of

communication materials were produced, ensuring consistent branding and messaging. The project's participation in conferences and scientific journals helped establish TELEMETRY's presence in relevant research and industry communities. Additionally, the first press release was issued to inform about the project. All scheduled activities for Year 1 have been successfully implemented and completed as planned.

Figure 2: Overview of dissemination and communication activities for Year 1

2.2.2 Year 2

In Year 2 of the TELEMETRY project (Figure 3), dissemination and communication efforts remain focused on expanding outreach, strengthening stakeholder engagement, and showcasing project results. The project website and social media channels are continuously updated with the latest news and developments, ensuring ongoing visibility and engagement.

To support outreach activities, new communication materials have been developed, and work has begun on a podcast series aimed at presenting project insights and outcomes in an accessible and engaging format. Additionally, targeted dissemination efforts have been initiated through the creation of specialised materials tailored to different stakeholder groups, ensuring that key audiences receive relevant information on the project's progress and impact. A press release and newsletters have also been published to highlight key milestones, with further editions planned throughout the year.

TELEMETRY is actively engaging with the research community by participating in conferences and publishing scientific journals on key project themes, ensuring that ongoing results are widely shared. A major initiative in this phase is the co-organization of the LIFESEC workshop at the 11th International Conference on Smart Computing (SmartComp 2025), providing a dedicated platform for deeper engagement with experts, researchers, and stakeholders.

From a collaboration and joint events perspective, although this activity should start on Month 24, TELEMETRY is actively involved in clustering and knowledge-sharing activities with key European cybersecurity initiatives. The project contributes to the European Clustering for Cybersecurity Certification -led by the EMERALD and COBALT EU projects- and collaborates with the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI), led by the FINSEC EU Project. These partnerships extend TELEMETRY's outreach to the industry and policy communities, fostering the exchange of expertise and strengthening the European cybersecurity ecosystem.

Beyond clustering activities, TELEMETRY is preparing to organize joint events and workshops with sister projects from the Increased Cybersecurity 2022 (HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01) EU Call. The project also seeks to enhance bilateral collaborations by sharing knowledge and exploring opportunities to test tools developed by other initiatives. To facilitate this, further discussions and collaboration workshops may be necessary to identify synergies and maximise impact.

These activities will continue throughout Year 2, ensuring that TELEMETRY effectively reaches its target audiences and maintains a strong level of engagement across various sectors.

Figure 3: Overview of dissemination and communication activities for Year 2

2.2.3 Year 3

In Year 3 of the TELEMETRY project (Figure 4), dissemination and communication activities will evolve dynamically, with the first six months focusing on the “*Inform & Connect*” & “*Demonstrate & Contribute*” phases, while in the final six months, all three phases will converge, ensuring a comprehensive communication effort. This approach will maximise the visibility, adoption, and long-term impact of TELEMETRY’s outcomes.

The project will continue to develop and update communication materials, ensuring effective dissemination of key findings. The website and social media channels will be regularly updated with news, project developments, and promotional materials. Additionally, press releases and newsletters will be published to highlight major milestones and sustain engagement with stakeholders. With the project’s tools finalised, targeted dissemination efforts will be strengthened by promoting specialised materials tailored to the target audiences, ensuring that TELEMETRY’s results will reach them.

TELEMETRY will actively participate in conferences, clustering events, and key industry discussions, ensuring broad communication of project outcomes. Research findings will be published in scientific journals and presented at high-profile cybersecurity and IoT forums.

Additionally, the project will organise a series of workshops, training sessions, and demonstrations, with some conducted internally and others externally, to showcase its innovations, foster knowledge exchange, and facilitate the adoption of its outcomes.

Figure 4: Overview of dissemination and communication activities for Year 3

3 Dissemination and Communication activities

This chapter provides an overview of the dissemination and communication activities carried out until Month 18. The project has been dedicated to enhancing visibility and stakeholder engagement through the website, social media, newsletters, press releases, and events. Partners have also contributed by participating in conferences, publishing research, and collaborating with EU and national initiatives.

3.1 Project website

The TELEMETRY project website (www.telemetry-project.eu), launched in March 2024, functions as a platform designed to gather and disseminate information about the project's objectives, activities, and outcomes. It serves as a resource for the target audience, the direct and indirect beneficiaries of the project. The website is continuously updated to ensure that the latest developments, findings, and project milestones are readily available. This includes detailed documentation on project deliverables, announcements of key achievements, news on ongoing research efforts, and updates on upcoming events, such as conferences and workshops. Through its structured sections, it allows users to navigate seamlessly through various aspects of the project, ensuring they have access to timely and relevant information that reflects the project's progress and impact. Figure 5 below presents the website's homepage.

Welcome to TELEMETRY project!

Cybersecurity via trustworthy tools and methodologies is a crucial challenge for IoT ecosystems.

Figure 5: TELEMETRY website homepage

The website features sections such as "*About TELEMETRY*", which outlines the project's mission, goals, and work packages, and "*Who We Are*", which presents the consortium partners and project team.

The Resources page serves as a central repository for all materials related to the TELEMETRY project, ensuring that target audiences can easily access and reference essential outputs. This section includes Publications, where users can explore research articles and papers authored by consortium members on topics relevant to TELEMETRY's thematic areas. The Deliverables subpage functions as an organised archive, listing all project deliverables, with only the publicly available ones uploaded.

Additionally, the "*Use Cases*" and "*Tools*" sections offer insights into the practical applications and technological advancements developed within TELEMETRY. To support broader dissemination, the "*Communication Material*" subpage provides downloadable content, including the project flyer, logo, and other promotional assets. These resources ensure that stakeholders, researchers, and industry professionals have access to comprehensive information on TELEMETRY's progress and contributions.

The "*News & Events*" page plays a crucial role in keeping the public and stakeholders informed about the latest updates, developments, and engagements related to TELEMETRY. The "*News*" subpage features recent announcements, project milestones, and progress updates, ensuring

visitors stay up to date with the project's advancements. Additionally, this section includes press releases and project material related to communication, such as newsletters, promotional content, and other dissemination materials, providing a central hub for TELEMETRY's outreach efforts. Some of these materials, including press releases, are available for download.

The “*Events*” subpage highlights conferences, workshops, and demonstrations organised under the project, providing opportunities for networking, knowledge exchange, and stakeholder engagement. This section ensures that audiences are aware of opportunities to participate in TELEMETRY-related activities and discussions.

The “*Blog*” page (Figure 6) serves as a knowledge hub where consortium partners, experts, and researchers contribute informative articles on topics relevant to the TELEMETRY project. It provides a platform for sharing insights, analyses, and updates on key developments in areas that TELEMETRY focuses on, ensuring that stakeholders stay informed about the latest trends, challenges, and advancements in cybersecurity, IoT security, and digital infrastructure resilience.

In addition to articles written by project partners, the blog will feature research-based analyses, highlighting findings from ongoing studies and investigations conducted within TELEMETRY. Our goal is not only to disseminate knowledge but also to foster engagement and collaboration. To this end, we aim to actively involve relevant stakeholders by inviting them to contribute articles that will be published on our blog. This approach will enhance the diversity of perspectives, encourage cross-sector dialogue, and further establish TELEMETRY as a key reference point in the field.

Figure 6: TELEMETRY Blog page

In January 2025, we launched a dedicated page titled “*IEEE SmartComp 2025*” (Figure 7) to provide all relevant information about the Workshop on Whole-Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC), co-organized by the TELEMETRY and DOSS projects, which will take place on 16 June 2025. For more details, please refer to Subsection 3.11.

This page serves as a resource for updates related to the workshop, ensuring that interested participants, researchers, and stakeholders have access to essential details. It will be continuously updated with the latest information, including deadlines, submission guidelines, and program details. At present, it features information about the workshop organisers and provides guidance for those interested in submitting and presenting their papers. As the event approaches, additional details -such as accepted papers, keynote speakers, and the final agenda- will be added to enhance clarity and accessibility for prospective attendees

Figure 7: TELEMETRY IEEE SmartComp 2025 page

At the time of finalising this deliverable (27th of February), the TELEMETRY project website had recorded 198 visitors and had 52 material downloads. This number is expected to increase significantly as dissemination activities expand, engagement with stakeholders grows, and the project progresses toward its milestones.

Notably, the website's engagement rate has seen a substantial increase, rising from 11.54% in March 2024, when the website launched, to 42.64% in February 2025. Additionally, the average time spent on the website has significantly improved, growing from just 12 seconds in March 2024 to 1 minute and 16 seconds in February 2025, with an average of 1 minute and 22 seconds. These trends indicate that visitors are increasingly interacting with the content, reflecting the effectiveness of ongoing updates, targeted outreach efforts, and enhanced visibility through events, publications, and social media promotion. Website traffic is anticipated to rise steadily over the coming months as these efforts continue.

3.2 Social media channels

Social media pages play a pivotal role in the TELEMETRY project's dissemination and communication strategy, enabling it to reach a diverse and broad audience. Social media platforms are among the most effective channels for sharing information due to their global reach, ease of access, and rapid information flow, making them essential tools for increasing project visibility and engagement.

The project has established official profiles on X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, and YouTube, ensuring a multi-platform approach tailored to different types of audiences and content.

3.2.1 LinkedIn

The TELEMETRY LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/telemetry-project>), established in April 2024, serves as an official communication channel, ensuring that information about TELEMETRY's objectives, progress, and findings reaches a well-defined and relevant audience.

Through regular updates, the page features project news, announcements, event highlights, and research insights, while also sharing relevant external content that aligns with TELEMETRY's thematic focus on cybersecurity, IoT security, and digital infrastructure resilience. By leveraging LinkedIn's professional networking environment, the page fosters interactions with stakeholders, industry experts, and researchers, encourages knowledge exchange, and helps build connections with experts and organisations working in related fields. Additionally, it supports the project's broader dissemination strategy by directing interested audiences to the TELEMETRY website for more in-depth information and resources. Figure 8 presents an overview of the TELEMETRY LinkedIn page.

Figure 8: TELEMETRY LinkedIn page

Using LinkedIn Analytics, we have gathered key insights and performance metrics for the TELEMETRY LinkedIn page. As shown in Table 2 below, the page has published 34 posts, attracted 42 followers and reached 3,368 users. Engagement levels include 90 likes, 44 shares, and 117 link clicks, demonstrating an initial but growing interest in the project's activities. These metrics reflect the early stages of our outreach efforts, and as dissemination activities continue to expand, we anticipate increased engagement and a broader reach in the following months.

Table 2: TELEMETRY LinkedIn analytics

Number of posts	34
Followers	42
Reach	3,368
Shares	44
Likes	90
Link Clicks	117

Metrics

Impressions ▾

- Organic 3,995
- Sponsored 0

Figure 9: TELEMTRY LinkedIn page impressions

Metrics

Members reached ▾

- Organic 2,115

Figure 10: TELEMTRY LinkedIn page members reached

3.2.2 X (Former Twitter)

The second communication channel established for the project is the X (formerly Twitter) account (https://x.com/TELEMETRY_EU), which serves as a complementary platform to LinkedIn but with a broader public reach. While LinkedIn primarily targets professionals, researchers, and industry stakeholders, X is widely used by a diverse audience, making it an effective tool for increasing public awareness and engagement. Due to the platform's character limit, messages are adapted to ensure clarity and impact, often incorporating visuals, infographics, and links to drive engagement. A key objective of the TELEMETRY X account is to direct traffic to the project's website, where users can find more detailed information about TELEMETRY's progress, findings, and upcoming activities.

Established in April 2024, the account has published 49 posts and has gained 19 followers. While the follower count is still in its early stages, continued activity, targeted content, and engagement with relevant communities are expected to enhance its reach and visibility over time. Figure 11 depicts the TELEMETRY X account.

Figure 11: TELEMETRY X (former Twitter) page

3.2.3 YouTube channel

The project has established a YouTube channel (Figure 12) as a dedicated platform for hosting and sharing video content related to TELEMETRY’s activities, findings, and events. This channel serves as an important audiovisual communication tool, allowing stakeholders to engage with the project through explanatory videos and other relevant materials that highlight its progress and findings.

To maximise its reach and impact, the YouTube channel is integrated with the project’s website, where videos will be embedded as needed to complement existing content and enhance accessibility. Additionally, videos will be promoted across TELEMETRY’s social media channels, ensuring broader visibility and engagement. This cross-platform integration helps generate traffic to the YouTube channel while directing viewers to the project’s website for more detailed information. To date we have 1 video and 18 subscribers.

Figure 12: TELEMETRY YouTube channel

3.3 Newsletter

The TELEMETRY project has utilized the Mailchimp platform to create and disseminate its newsletter, serving as a communication tool to keep stakeholders and the wider audience informed about the project's latest news, achievements, and developments. The newsletter provides updates on TELEMETRY’s progress, milestones, and upcoming events, ensuring that relevant audiences remain engaged and well-informed about the project's scope and impact.

So far, two newsletters have been released (available in Annex 8.1.1). The first, sent on 12 September 2024, provided a general introduction to the project, outlining its objectives and highlighting key aspects of the first project meeting. The second newsletter (12 February 2025) focused on the announcement of the LIFESEC workshop, covering topics of interest, workshop highlights, and other relevant information. Each newsletter includes brief descriptions of key topics, along with buttons featuring hyperlinks that redirect readers to the TELEMETRY website, where they can access more in-depth information.

In Figure 13, screenshots from sections of the first (right) and second (left) newsletters can be seen. At the bottom of each newsletter, the logos of all project partners are displayed, alongside the EU disclaimer, ensuring transparency and proper acknowledgment of the project's funding.

Figure 13: TELEMETRY Newsletter – The first newsletter (right) and the second newsletter (left)

Until now, the TELEMETRY newsletter has 23 subscribers, with efforts ongoing to expand its reach. To maximise outreach, the newsletters are not only sent to subscribers but are also distributed via TELEMETRY’s social media channels, ensuring wider dissemination and engagement. As the project progresses and awareness grows, the number of subscribers is expected to increase.

3.4 Press releases

As part of its dissemination efforts, the TELEMETRY project has utilised press releases to enhance awareness and communicate its latest developments. So far, two press releases have been published (Figure 14) to broaden the project's reach. The first press release, published on 28 May 2024, introduced the project to the general public by outlining its objectives, aims, and consortium partners. It also included a quote from the project coordinator, providing insights into the project's vision and expected impact. Each press release includes all the necessary acknowledgments, such as the EU flag and disclaimer, ensuring proper recognition of the project's funding (available in Annex 8.1.2).

The second press release, published on 24 January 2025, focused on the LIFESEC workshop, informing stakeholders about its purpose and participation opportunities while encouraging interested researchers to submit their papers. This release played a significant role in promoting the workshop.

Figure 14: TELEMETRY press releases – The first press release (right) and the second press release (left)

The press releases were uploaded on the project's website and distributed through TELEMETRY's social media accounts to enhance visibility. Additionally, they were shared with consortium partners, who further disseminated them within their networks and broader collaborating organisations.

3.5 Project video

A promotional video has been created and published on the TELEMETRY YouTube channel¹, serving as an introduction to the project. The video provides an overview of TELEMETRY's aims, objectives, and pilot programs, while highlighting its focus on its primary target groups, the Component Developers (CDs), the System Integrators (SIs), and the System Operators (SOs). Additionally, it presents the expected project impact, consortium partners, and communication channels, ensuring clear and accessible information for stakeholders and the broader audience.

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Suq001plfg0>

Figure 15: TELEMETRY video (frames)

3.6 Scientific publications and conferences

In addition to journal publications mentioned in the previous subsection, TELEMETRY aims to publish scientific results at internationally recognised conferences, where generally a TELEMETRY member attends the conference and presents the publication. To that end, several conference and journal papers have been published so far as listed below, with a journal publication currently under review. In addition, TELEMETRY has proposed a workshop in collaboration with the DOSS project that has been accepted for the upcoming IEEE SmartComp 2025 conference, which provides an excellent platform for further dissemination activities. For further details on the workshop, please see section 3.11.

3.6.1 Conference publications in the current reporting period

During the first 18 months, TELEMETRY research partners have published five articles in peer-reviewed conference proceedings, all of which have been assigned a PID.

1. Jaatun, L.A., Sørlien, S.M., Borgaonkar, R., Taylor, S. and Jaatun, M.G., 2023, December. Software Bill of Materials in Critical Infrastructure. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom)* (pp. 319-324). [Contributing partners: SINTEF, UoS]

2. Taylor, S., Jaatun, M.G., McGibney, A., Seidl, R., Hrynchenko, P., Prosvirin, D. and Mancilla, R., 2024. A Framework Addressing Challenges in Cybersecurity Testing of IoT Ecosystems and Components. In *IoT BDS 2024 Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Internet of Things, Big Data and Security*. [Contributing partners: UoS, SINTEF, MTU, Nokia, WRCVE, Antonov, ENG]
3. Lytvyn, V., Bakurova, A., Zaritskyi, O., Gritskevich, A., Hrynchenko, P., Tereschenko, E. and Shyrokorad, D., 2024. Fuzzy logic-based methodology for building access control systems based on fuzzy logic. In *MoDaST-2024: 6th International Workshop on Modern Data Science Technologies*. [Contributing partner: WRCVE]
4. Holmdin, N. and Jaatun, M.G., 2024, November. Fuzz Testing of a Wireless Residential Gateway. In *Norsk IKT-konferanse for forskning og utdanning* (No. 3). [Contributing partner: SINTEF]
5. Bakurova, Anna V., Zaritskyi, Oleh V., Gritskevich Anatoliy A., Hrynchenko, Pavlo V. Tereschenko, Elina V., Shyrokorad, Dmytro V., 2024, Assessment Of The Vulnerability Of The Information System Based On Fuzzy Mathematics. In *The Twenty Sixth International Scientific and Practical Seminar "COMBINATORIAL CONFIGURATIONS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS" is dedicated to the memory of Professor G.A. Dontsia, June 13-15, 2024* (pp. 19-24) (ISBN 978-617-7942-27-5). <https://zp.edu.ua/conference-2024-1-4> [Contributing partner: WRCVE]

Additionally, four more peer-reviewed publications (one journal and three conference publications) have been submitted, but as of the submission of this deliverable, they have not yet been assigned a PID.

1. Oleh Zaritskyi. Expert system for assessing the status of the access control system to the information environment of a Smart factory. Accepted in International Scientific Technical Journal «Problems of Control and Informatics» (PC&I), Artificial intelligence systems. 2025, (ISSN 2786-6491) [Contributing Partner: WRCVE]
2. Bakurova, Anna V., Zaritskyi, Oleh V., Gritskevich Anatoliy A., Hrynchenko, Pavlo V. Tereschenko, Elina V., Shyrokorad, Dmytro V., 2024, Assessment Of The Consequences Of Vulnerabilities In Network Systems. In *XII International Scientific and Practical Conference CURRENT PROBLEMS AND ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE FIELD OF RADIO TECHNOLOGY OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES (December 10-12, 2024, Zaporizhzhya)* (pp. 429-432). ISBN 978-617-529-487-1 <https://zp.edu.ua/conference-2024-1-4> [Contributing partners: WRCVE]
3. Gritskevich, Anatoliy A., 2024, Determining Anomalous Behavior Of Entities In Large It Structures. In *XII International Scientific and Practical Conference CURRENT PROBLEMS AND ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE FIELD OF RADIO TECHNOLOGY OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES (December 10-12, 2024, Zaporizhzhya)* (pp. 433-437). (ISBN 978-617-529-487-1), (<https://zp.edu.ua/conference-2024-1-4>) [Contributing partners: WRCVE]
4. Taylor, S., Götze, N., Kuhr, J., Abendroth, J., Zaritskyi, O., Mancilla, R., Wenning, B.-L., Kuruppuarachchi, P., Omerovic, A., Borgaonkar, R., Skytterholm, A.N., Mpantis, A., Triantafyllou, G., Garcia Perales, O., Cybersecurity Indicators Within a Cybersecurity Testing and Monitoring Framework. Accepted at IoT BDS 2025. [Contributing partners: UoS, Nokia, WRCVE, ENG, MTU, SINTEF, ATC, I4RI]

3.6.2 Journal and conference publications under review

One journal article is currently under review and has been submitted to Springer Nature Computer Science, contributing to TELEMETRY's scientific dissemination efforts. The article, titled "Toward Cybersecurity Testing and Monitoring of IoT Systems" is expected to further strengthen the project's impact within the research community.

The full citation of the article under review is provided below:

- Taylor, S., Melas, P., Jaatun, M.G., Omerovic, A., Seidl, R., Götze, N., Prosvirin, D., Leone, M., De Lutiis, P., Gritskevich, A., Triantafyllou, G., Mpantis, A, Garcia Perales, O., Wenning, B.-L., Dutttagupta, S., Toward Cybersecurity Testing and Monitoring of IoT Systems. Submitted to Springer Nature Computer Science. [Contributing partners: UoS, SINTEF, Nokia, Antonov, TIM, WRCVE, ATC, I4RI, MTU, KUL]

3.6.3 Student conferences and student conferences publications

Disseminating the TELEMETRY project goals and progress is a strategic approach to broadening the interested audience around the topic of cybersecurity. Presenting the research results obtained during the TELEMETRY project at student conferences contributes to building a community of students and young scientists who are interested in developing IoT ecosystems & cybersecurity. The research results were presented at conferences by PhD students who conducted research within the TELEMETRY project. Plenary presentations were also given by researchers who are leading developments within the TELEMETRY project.

Figure 16: Screenshot from WRCVE’s presentation during the I (VII) International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists²

Among TELEMETRY’s participation in student conferences, there was also a peer-reviewed presentation titled "Advantages of a Network Attack Detection System (NADS) Using Wavelet Analysis". The full citation is provided below:

- Hrynchenko, P.V., 2024. Advantages of a Network Attack Detection System (NADS) Using Wavelet Analysis. In *ITTP2024: I (VII) International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists "Information Technologies: Theory and Practice" March 20-22, 2024* (pp. 32-35) (ISBN 978-617-627-182-6). [Contributing partners: WRCVE]

3.7 Partner’s networks

Leveraging TELEMETRY’s partner network to disseminate the project’s objectives and progress is a strategic approach aimed at reaching broader audiences, fostering collaboration, and strengthening the cybersecurity community. By utilising existing connections, the project enhances its visibility, engagement, and long-term impact, ensuring effective dissemination and collaboration among related initiatives.

TELEMETRY’s partners maintain extensive networks across various domains, including cybersecurity, allowing them to play a key role in spreading awareness about the project’s advancements. As part of their dissemination responsibilities, partners actively engage with

² The I (VII) International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists «Information Technologies: Theory and Practice» took place in 20-22 March 2024 and was organised by the Dnipro Polytechnic. Due to martial law, most national conferences in Ukraine are being held online.

their networks to share project updates, promote knowledge exchange, and identify potential collaboration opportunities.

In line with these efforts, Table 3 below presents the dissemination actions carried out by each partner up to Month 18 to support TELEMETRY’s outreach and engagement strategy.

Table 3: List of actions with partner’s networks

Partner	Actions carried
SINTEF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On 23 October 2024 TELEMETRY included in a meetup presentation at the Joint meeting of ISF/ISACA/CSA/Dataforeningen (in Norwegian). (available in Annex 8.2) • On 26 November 2024 TELEMETRY presented during a webinar for security champions of DNB (Norway’s largest bank) titled “SBOM – Soporific, or an Explosive Cocktail?”.
MTU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hosted an event with Cork’s Technology Network CEIA on 29 November 2024 where, among other presentations and demos of our research activities, MTU presented an overview of TELEMETRY and MTU’s role in the project. (Figure 17)
i4RI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Had a meeting with several projects in November hosted in Blackpool (UK), where i4RI is a partner. This meeting was organized by ICE with which i4RI has a close relationship. • Shared experiences, knowledge and developments with partners from other projects. (Figure 18)
KU Leuven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KUL gave a seminar on 5th September 2024 entitled “Threat Modeling for Industrial Control Systems” to a group of people from the Belgian SMEs, working in the industrial security sector. The seminar was about threat modelling and risk management methodologies for industrial systems and KUL gave an overview of the proposed alternatives to STRIDE.
Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENG is collaborating with ECSO to organize an online workshop in May 2025. The event will bring together projects, including TELEMETRY, that were funded under the CS-01-02 call to present their exploitation strategies. Currently, the selection criteria for determining which projects will be featured in the workshop are being finalized.
Antonov	<p>Antonov in collaboration with National Aviation University has arranged below conferences and research works were an overview of TELEMETRY and Antonov role in the project were presented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International scientific conference “<i>Sustainable Development of the Global Communication, Navigation, Surveillance and Air Traffic Management Systems</i>”, CNS/ATM May 29-31, 2023, National Aviation University, Kyiv, Ukraine

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XVI International Scientific and Technical Conference "AVIA-2023", APRIL 18-20, 2023 • 2nd International Workshop on <i>Advances in Civil Aviation Systems Development 2024</i> (March 26-27, 2024) • <i>ADP'24: International Workshop on Algorithms of Data Processing</i>, November 5, 2024, Kyiv, Ukraine • CARGO monitoring system was presented to Bollore Company and Airbus Company • Collaborated with partners from other projects to share experiences, knowledge, and advancements. • RESEARCH WORK № 310-ДБ20: Structural-parametric synthesis and development of technology for building solar-energy stratospheric platforms with adaptive neural control • RESEARCH WORK № 443-ДБ23: Development of an adaptively integrated noise-tolerant navigation system for controlling dynamic objects
<p>UOS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussed plan for risk management community with key contacts U Warwick and SINTEF.

Figure 17: Photo from Bernd Ludwig Wenning's (MTU) presentation.

Figure 18: Photo from Oscar Garcia's (i4RI) presentation.

Figure 19: ANTONOV's presentation during the International Workshop on Algorithms of Data Processing in Kyiv, Ukraine

3.8 Clustering (Liaison) activities with other EU projects

The objective of clustering activities is to enhance the technical and social impact of TELEMETRY’s results at the European level. This is achieved through collaborative technical discussions with other EU-funded projects, fostering knowledge exchange and strengthening synergies in the cybersecurity domain. Clustering (or Liaison) activities are closely linked to partner network actions, as many TELEMETRY partners are actively engaged in cybersecurity initiatives or other EU projects where cybersecurity is a key focus area.

While these activities were initially planned to begin on Month 24, TELEMETRY partners recognised the importance of early engagement to allow for longer-term collaboration and more targeted actions. As a result, these efforts were initiated ahead of schedule, enabling stronger connections and more strategic partnerships. Over the past months, several preliminary meetings have taken place to establish these collaborations and lay the groundwork for future joint activities. The details of these meetings, conducted up to Month 18, are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Report on Clustering activities

Project	Actions carried
NEMECYS GA no: 101094323	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share of knowledge, methodologies and tools • Direct participation of TELEMETRY partners in NEMECYS
EMERALD GA no: 101120688	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of ideas for collaboration • Bilateral call between the two projects
CERTIFAI GA no: 101120606	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of ideas for collaboration • Bilateral call between the two projects
SEC4AI4SEC GA no: 101120393	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of ideas for collaboration • Bilateral call between the two projects
DOSS GA no: 101120270	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-organization of a Workshop on Whole-Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC) in the context of the 11th IEEE International Conference on Smart Computing (SmartComp 2025) • Discussions for TELEMETRY’s participation in a webinar for the IoTDay (April 9th)

Additionally, TELEMETRY has officially joined the European Clustering for Cybersecurity Certification, an initiative established through the collaboration of the EMERALD and COBALT EU projects (<https://cybersecuritycertcluster.eu/>). This cluster is envisioned to provide a forum for discussion and collaboration for research and innovation initiatives that address the challenges and issues of Next Generation Agile Certification from various perspectives and approaches. Its main objective is to foster collaboration among existing research initiatives,

creating a critical mass of projects to share experiences, collaborate on approaches in order to elaborate a broad EU perspective, and discuss challenges for adoption and future research.

The EU projects that are currently engaged in this Cluster are the following:

- EMERALD (<https://www.emerald-he.eu/>)
- COBALT (<https://horizon-cobalt.eu/>)
- CERTIFAI (<https://certifai.info/>)
- DOSS (<https://dossproject.eu/>)
- CERTIFY (<https://certify-project.eu/>)
- TELEMETRY (<https://telemetry-project.eu/>)

TELEMETRY is a contributor of the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI), further strengthening its collaboration with EU-funded cybersecurity initiatives. The cluster, established by the FINSEC EU project along with other cybersecurity projects, aims to create synergies and drive innovation by fostering cross-project cooperation and knowledge exchange, particularly in the protection of critical infrastructures and essential services.

As a participant in ECSCI, TELEMETRY contributes to joint research efforts, discussions, and clustering activities, supporting the development of emerging disruptive solutions to security challenges. The research activities within the cluster focus on different approaches to safeguarding critical infrastructure, facilitating the development of complementary methodologies and strengthening connections between participating projects.

Currently, 47 EU projects are part of ECSCI, and TELEMETRY actively engages in events, discussions, and upcoming initiatives aimed at enhancing collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the overall impact of cybersecurity research across Europe.

3.9 Synergies with EU initiatives

The following table provides an overview of TELEMETRY's engagement with various European initiatives, highlighting the partners involved, their level of participation, and the specific actions undertaken. These synergies play a crucial role in strengthening collaboration, fostering knowledge exchange, and aligning TELEMETRY's efforts with broader EU strategies. By actively engaging with these initiatives, the project enhances its visibility, contributes to cross-sector discussions, and ensures that its outcomes are effectively integrated into the wider research and innovation ecosystem.

Table 5: Report on EU Initiatives

EU initiative	Partner(s) Involved	Level of Participation	Specific Actions Taken
<p>ECSSO European Cyber Security Organization https://www.ecsso.org.eu/</p>	<p>ENG, MTU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENG: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ participates in monthly meetings and engages in discussions based on the specific topic. ○ is actively involved in general participation in initiative meetings. ○ ENG follows the specific WG: Policy Analysis and Outreach Stream, Trusted Supply Chains, Cybersecurity Market Development, Cyber Threat Management (CTI Initiative, NIS2 Implementation Initiative), Skills & Human Factors - Road2Cyber, Technologies & Innovation and Defence & Space. • MTU is actively involved in working groups, with a particular focus on WG5 “Skills & Human Factors - Road2Cyber”. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TELEMETRY was presented at the WG6 “Technologies & Innovation and Defence & Space” by ENG. • Discussions on possible participation of TELEMETRY in an upcoming workshop organized by WG6.
<p>Big Data Value Association (BDVA) www.bdva.eu</p>	<p>ATC, SINTEF, NOKIA, ENG</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project partners contributed to some actions within the initiative. • Engineering is a founding member of the association and is represented in the Board of Directors since the beginning. Currently, is active on several key working groups as co-leader: Smart Manufacturing Industry, Smart Governance and Smart Cities, AgriFood, Energy, Security. Additionally, is contributing to the main yearly events organized by the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENG and NOKIA are assessing which projects and initiatives within the telecommunications group, represented by Robert (NOKIA), could be engaged in workshops focused on exploitation activities.

		Association (namely, Data Week and European Big Data Value Forum) as chair of tracks, session promoter and speaker, leveraging and amount of active R&D projects coordinated or participated.	
ENISA - European Union Agency for Cybersecurity	TIM, NOKIA	NOKIA and TIM are involved in ENISA's Ad Hoc Working Groups (AHWG), with NOKIA and TIM participating in 5G discussions and TIM contributing to eSIM certification efforts.	Discussions held in which WG and initiatives TELEMETRY would be involved.

3.10 Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms

The objective of this activity is to establish and strengthen collaborations with national and regional initiatives, funding programs, and platforms that align with TELEMETRY's goals. By fostering these synergies, the project seeks to leverage existing resources, expertise, and networks to maximise its impact and contribute to the broader EU research and innovation landscape.

In this context, several meetings have taken place in recent months to initiate and advance these collaborations. The details of these meetings are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Report on Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms

National or regional initiative	Partner(s) involved	Actions carried
UK National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/	UoS	UoS hosts GCHQ Academic Centre of excellence for CyberSec research and UoS CyberSec Academy. Both are directly linked to industry, the CyberSec community and NCSC.
IloT-SBOM - Security and Software Bill of Materials for IoT https://www.iiootsbom.com/	KUL	IloT-SBOM was a project executed locally in Flanders and KU Leuven was one of the project partners. The project ended in December 2024. It was developed as an action to support companies in Flanders, Belgium and Europe to create awareness on ongoing

		<p>developments to CyberSecure equipment and machinery in production environments in the first place, in order for the manufacturers to be able focus on their core activities. The technical focus of the project was on SBOMs (software and security bill of materials) and how SBOMs can be used in IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things) to improve the overall security.</p> <p>The main activity of KU Leuven within IIoT-SBOM was (i) giving seminars and webinars on SBOMs / IIoT security, (ii) applied research on IIoT and SBOM security and (iii) writing whitepapers and academic papers on the aforementioned topics.</p> <p>Being a member of both projects (TELEMETRY and IIoT-SBOM), KU Leuven acts as a liaison and therefore can share insights from both projects.</p>
National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI)	MTU	Continuous engagement on national mirror committees. Specifically, MTU provided contributions to drafting standard ISO/TC 307/WG 7 Interoperability as part of ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies. This is relevant in terms of MTU activities on DLT within TELEMETRY.
International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) - https://international.dataspaces.org	MTU	Active in the Architecture WG, where MTU contributions are informed by ongoing research projects including the TELEMETRY.
Computer Emergency Response Team of Ukraine - https://cert.gov.ua/	WRCVE	Work has been carried out to inform the management of the Computer Emergency Response Team of Ukraine about the goals and objectives of the project. Consultations are underway on possible cooperation in disseminating the project results.
Scientific Cyber Security Association of Ukraine - https://scsa.org.ua/	WRCVE	Similar work has been carried out to inform the management of the Scientific Cyber Security Association of Ukraine of Ukraine about the goals of the project. Consultations are underway on possible cooperation in disseminating the project results.
OpenChain https://openchainproject.org/	NOKIA	Nokia is leading the Telco WG in the OpenChain community. Nokia released a SBOM validator as open source. A script to validate SBOMs against the OpenChain Telco SBOM Guide. The validator is available in PyPI: https://openchainproject.org/news/2024/09/29/nok

[ia-contributes-validator-for-the-openchain-telco-sbom-guide-2](#)

3.11 Workshops

Over the past 18 months, TELEMETRY has initiated the organisation of workshops aimed at fostering knowledge exchange, collaboration, and the exploitation of project results. These efforts have now commenced and will continue to evolve in the coming months.

One initiative is the workshop co-organized by TELEMETRY and the DOSS projects at the IEEE SmartComp 2025 conference, which will take place in Cork, Ireland, on 16th June 2025. Titled “Whole-Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC)”, this workshop is designed to attract publications focused on cybersecurity methodologies and tools across all stages of the smart system lifecycle. It will be chaired by Robert Seidl (Nokia) and Bernd-Ludwig Wenning (MTU) from TELEMETRY, alongside Antonio Skarmeta (University of Murcia) from the DOSS project. The Technical Program Committee (TPC) consists of experts beyond the TELEMETRY consortium, bringing diverse perspectives and expertise to the workshop.

Spyridoula Markou (ATC) serves as the Publicity Chair, leading TELEMETRY’s efforts in communication and dissemination for the LIFESEC Workshop. As part of these efforts, TELEMETRY has developed press releases (*Subsection 3.4*), newsletters (*Subsection 3.3*), and social media graphics (Figure 20) to enhance outreach and engagement. Additionally, a promotional video is currently being finalized to further amplify the call for participation.

Figure 20: Sample of LIFESEC workshop graphic

Additionally, ENG has developed a structured plan for a workshop series aimed at enhancing exploitation strategies across multiple projects. The plan consists of three key phases:

1. An initial online session where participants present their exploitation strategies at both the project and individual result levels.
2. A second in-person meeting to deepen discussions, foster collaboration, and identify concrete synergies.
3. A final phase at a European event, where key outcomes and joint initiatives will be showcased to a wider audience.

These structured efforts aim to maximise knowledge sharing, reinforce inter-project cooperation, and enhance the impact of TELEMETRY's exploitation activities. The organisation of these workshops is an ongoing process, with further activities planned in the upcoming months.

3.12 TELEMETRY in external communications

Beyond its own dissemination efforts, TELEMETRY has gained visibility and recognition through mentions by consortium partners and other EU-funded projects. These references, whether through social media posts, project websites, newsletters, or research publications, contribute to broadening TELEMETRY's outreach, reinforcing its presence within the cybersecurity and IoT ecosystem, and fostering collaboration across initiatives.

This chapter provides an overview of how TELEMETRY and its partners have been featured in external communications, showcasing the project's growing influence and engagement within the European research and innovation landscape. These mentions not only enhance awareness but also highlight TELEMETRY's role in knowledge-sharing, cross-project synergies, and joint research efforts.

3.12.1 Partners activities

During the first 18 months of the project, TELEMETRY partners have significantly enhanced the project's visibility, activities, and results by expanding its online presence. This has been achieved through the creation of dedicated project pages, news updates on their respective websites, and the active sharing of TELEMETRY-related content across institutional social media channels. Examples of these posts are shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22³.

³ I4RI's post can be found [here](#) and ATC's post [here](#).

Please, check blog post published by @TELEMETRY_EU : Forging a Secure Future: Key Principles of IoT Cybersecurity in Manufacturing

telemetry-project.eu/forging-a-secu...

#Cybersecurity #HorizonEurope

From telemetry-project.eu

Figure 22: Example from post in i4RI's X account

#SaveTheDate: 16th June 2025 | Cork, Ireland

#TELEMETRY_eu and DOSS EU are organising the Workshop on Whole-Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC), during IEEE SmartComp 2025, which will explore cutting-edge methodologies to ensure secure and trustworthy hardware and software across all phases of development and deployment.

Check more information below

Heard the news? #TELEMETRY_eu in collaboration with DOSS EU, is organising the Workshop on Whole-Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC), during IEEE SmartComp 2025!

This workshop will explore cutting-edge methodologies to ensure secure and trustworthy hardware and software across all phases of development and deployment.

#SaveTheDate: 16th June 2025 | Cork, Ireland

Call for Papers: We invite researchers and practitioners to share insights on securing hardware and software throughout their lifecycle!

Figure 21: Example from post in ATC's LinkedIn account

3.12.2 TELEMETRY in external dissemination efforts

This section highlights the mentions of TELEMETRY by other EU-funded projects. These references, whether through social media posts and website updates contribute to expanding TELEMETRY's visibility and strengthening its presence. Examples of these posts are shown in Figure 23 and Figure 24⁴.

⁴ The archived version of the DOSS project website homepage can be accessed [here](#). Additionally, the post on the DOSS X account is available [here](#).

Figure 23: TELEMETRY mention in DOSS project website

Figure 24: TELEMETRY mentioned in DOSS X account

4 Project materials

Effective visual identity and communication materials are essential for ensuring a consistent and professional representation of the TELEMETRY project. This chapter provides an overview of the branding elements and dissemination materials developed to enhance the project's visibility and outreach. It details the visual identity and logo, which establish a recognisable brand for TELEMETRY, as well as the document templates, including the official PowerPoint presentation and Word templates, ensuring uniformity in project-related materials. Additionally, the chapter presents the visuals, project flyer, and project banner, which serve as key tools for promoting TELEMETRY across various communication channels, events, and stakeholder engagements.

4.1 Visual identity and logo

A strong visual identity has been created for TELEMETRY, as showcased in Deliverable “D5.1 *Dissemination & Communication Plan*”.

The logo (Figure 25) was designed according to the project's theme, aligning with trustworthiness, open knowledge, automation, and security testing for IoT ecosystems.

- The first element is an outline of the capital “T” rotated 45° for emphasis and optical interest.
- The small dots on the first element of the logo represent the process of the remote sources that collect the data.
- A simplified all capital full name of the project with the twist of certain corners that are converted, adds more character and becomes easier to recognize.

Figure 25: TELEMETRY Logo

Figure 26: TELEMETRY Logo – versions adapting to different backgrounds

An icon version of the logo (Figure 27) has also been created and is used in communication materials.

Figure 27: TELEMETRY icon

During project communication, the logo or icon version is used alongside the EU funding information. To ensure a consistent communication strategy, a brand guide was developed and shared with all consortium partners. This guide includes logo usage, colour scheme, typography, imagery, and other brand elements.

4.2 Document templates

To ensure a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy, relevant documents were created and distributed to all partners. These materials are intended for use as needed to support the project's promotion.

4.2.1 Project PPT presentation

The presentation is one of the project's tools designed to support dissemination efforts. It is intended for all partners to use when presenting the project or its outcomes at various events. In Figure 28, you can see the two presentation templates created to accommodate partners' needs: a light version and a dark version.

Figure 28: TELEMETRY's ppt presentations

4.2.2 Project word templates

While in Deliverable “D5.1 *Dissemination & Communication Plan*” reported the development of a word template, additional word templates were created to better address the project's needs. These templates ensure consistency across various project documents, including reports, deliverables, and meeting minutes, providing partners with a standardised format for effective communication and documentation.

The templates created include:

- Deliverable template
- Meeting minutes template
- Project report per WP template
- Project report per partner template
- Peer review template
- Agenda template
- General template
- Press release template

4.3 Visuals

A variety of visuals have been designed to highlight the project's activities and results on social media, ensuring alignment with the TELEMETRY visual identity. To maintain consistency across communication efforts, each visual incorporates the project logo or icon. Figure 29 presents examples of graphics created to promote the project, showcase articles published on the project blog, and encourage newsletter subscriptions.

Figure 29: TELEMETRY's visuals

4.4 Project flyer

To further disseminate the project and its partners, we have developed a tri-fold flyer that provides an overview of the project, its aim, the partners involved, as well as contact information for further communication. The flyer includes a QR code that directs users to the project website, offering detailed information on its objectives, results, and expected impact. Its purpose is to enhance awareness and visibility while serving as a key communication tool at major events and conferences, where project partners will distribute it. Figure 30 below illustrates the project's flyer.

Project partners

NOCIA, SINTEF, MTU, Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, A.T.C., KU LEUVEN, TIM, eng, WRCVE, University of Southampton

Contact us

QR code

Info@telemetry-project.eu
@TELEMETRY_EU
Telemetry project
@TELEMETRY_EU

Advancing IoT Cybersecurity with Trustworthy Tools & Innovations

The project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101119747. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

By developing cutting-edge tools and methodologies, TELEMETRY aims to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities in complex systems from various industrial sectors, such as telecom, aerospace, and manufacturing. Our approach ensures resilient and secure digital infrastructures through continuous risk assessment and real-time anomaly detection.

Our expectations:
We envision our tools enhancing cybersecurity across various industries, benefiting businesses and citizens alike. By collaborating with experts, we are shaping a safer IoT landscape for the future.

What we do:
We create and validate innovative tools to detect security vulnerabilities in IoT environments. Our solutions, tested in real-world pilots, improve threat detection accuracy and reduce the cost of verification.

Our aim:
TELEMETRY focuses on building resilient IoT infrastructures. We aim to protect systems throughout their lifecycle—from design to operation—by providing reliable tools for vulnerability detection and secure updates.

TELEMETRY is set to revolutionize the security landscape of IoT devices and systems.

Figure 30: TELEMETRY's flyer

4.5 Project banner

To enhance the project's visibility at key events and conferences, a dedicated TELEMETRY project banner (Figure 31) has been designed. This banner serves as a visual representation of the project, reinforcing its identity and ensuring a strong presence in various dissemination activities. It is used at events organised by the project, as well as at external conferences where TELEMETRY is represented, helping to attract attention and engage stakeholders.

Figure 31: TELEMETRY's banner

5 Dissemination and Communication Impact Assessment

This section evaluates the impact of TELEMETRY’s dissemination and communication activities by comparing their quantitative indicators against the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) established in Deliverable 5.1 “Dissemination & Communication Plan” and the Grand Agreement.

Based on the KPIs and their descriptions, and considering the dissemination and communication efforts carried out so far, Table 7 provides an overview of how effective these activities have been during the first 18 months of the project.

It is important to note that most key dissemination and communication activities are ongoing, as expected at M18, and are marked with an orange status, indicating they are still in progress. The project will continue to track and assess KPI progress to ensure that all key dissemination and communication goals are met by the end of Year 3.

Table 7: TELEMETRY’s Dissemination and Communication KPIs tracking for M1-M18

Indicator	KPIs Y1-Y3	KPIs achieved M1-M18	Status
Project website	1000+ web page visits per year; 200+ material downloads per year	198 web page visits; 52 downloads	In progress
Collaboration with relevant EU projects	>4. At least 1 meeting per year & 1 joint activity.	1 joint event (November 2024)	In progress
Liaison with relevant EU communities	Representation and active participation of TELEMETRY on 4+ working groups by project end.	1 working group	In progress
Scientific publications and presentations at conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.	20+ journal papers and conference papers accepted over the duration of TELEMETRY; participation in 15+ events.	9 papers accepted or published; participation in 7 conferences and workshops	In progress

Press releases	5+ press releases	2	In progress
Newsletters	6+ newsletters	2	In progress
Videos	2+ promotional project videos	1	In progress
Brochures	1500+ Brochure (flyers) distribution	350	In progress

6 Future plans

As TELEMETRY progresses into the next phase of the project, dissemination and communication activities will continue to evolve to enhance outreach, engagement, and impact. This section outlines the planned actions across various dissemination and communication categories, detailing the activities that different TELEMETRY partners will implement in the upcoming months.

Building on the foundations established during the first 18 months, these future efforts will amplify the project's visibility, ensure greater engagement with key stakeholders, and enhance the adoption of TELEMETRY's results. The planned activities will focus on scientific publications, participation in international conferences, collaborative clustering initiatives, training sessions, and targeted communication campaigns. Furthermore, upcoming actions will emphasise the promotion of the project's tools and methodologies, as more concrete outputs become available.

Among the key areas of focus will be the enhancement of the project's online presence, including continuous updates to the website and social media channels, as well as the release of new communication materials, such as videos, podcasts, newsletters, and targeted outreach campaigns. Special emphasis will be placed on promoting TELEMETRY's participation in major events, including the LIFESEC workshop at IEEE SmartComp 2025, and ensuring that stakeholders remain informed and engaged.

Additionally, TELEMETRY partners will expand collaborations with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, strengthening knowledge-sharing and cross-project synergies. Efforts will also focus on furthering engagement with policymakers and industry professionals, ensuring that the project's findings contribute to ongoing discussions on cybersecurity, IoT security, and risk management strategies.

It is important to note that while the following subsections provide a detailed breakdown of the known planned activities, additional actions may be identified and implemented as the project evolves. Dissemination and communication efforts will remain dynamic and responsive, adapting to emerging opportunities, stakeholder needs, and project developments to strengthen TELEMETRY's long-term impact.

6.1 Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plans

Looking ahead, TELEMETRY will focus on expanding and enhancing its dissemination and communication efforts to amplify the project's visibility, engagement, and long-term impact.

A priority will be the continuous development of the project website, incorporating detailed information on tools and use cases as they become available. Throughout its communication channels scientific publications and conference participation will be promoted, ensuring that key findings reach the relevant communities. The LIFESEC workshop will be widely promoted through TELEMETRY's channels, encouraging participation from stakeholders across multiple sectors.

TELEMETRY will continue to strengthen its dissemination and communication activities through various targeted initiatives. Upcoming efforts will include the publication of press releases and newsletters, ensuring that project updates, milestones, and developments reach a broad audience.

Additionally, tailored materials will be developed to engage specific stakeholder groups, including videos, flyers, and other multimedia content. An updated version of the project flyer will be created to reflect new developments and findings.

The podcast series, currently under development, will be finalised and serve as an essential tool for outreach, providing insights into TELEMETRY's progress, research publications, and policy implications. These podcasts will be designed to inform policymakers and regulators, offering discussions on policy recommendations, compliance, and regulatory aspects related to cybersecurity and IoT security.

Beyond these initiatives, TELEMETRY will work to increase social media engagement, expand its audience, and introduce more interactive and engaging content. Additionally, the project will explore collaborations with external initiatives and EU projects to optimize its dissemination efforts and extend its reach.

All communication efforts will continue to be promoted through the project's established channels, including the website, social media, and direct stakeholder engagement, with a focus on demonstrating TELEMETRY's practical applications and impact. Through these efforts, TELEMETRY aims to strengthen its presence within the research and cybersecurity communities, ensure the adoption of its results, and enhance the sustainability of its outcomes beyond the project's duration.

6.2 International conferences and stands

The TELEMETRY project and its partners will continue to maintain a strong presence at international conferences and industry events, ensuring the dissemination of research findings, project developments, and outcomes to a broad audience of experts, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. These events provide valuable opportunities for networking, collaboration, and knowledge exchange, allowing TELEMETRY to engage with relevant communities, showcase its progress, and strengthen synergies with other initiatives.

In Table 8, an indicative list of international conferences and stands where TELEMETRY and its partners plan to participate is provided, reflecting the project's ongoing commitment to outreach and engagement at the European and global levels.

Table 8: Indicative list of international conferences

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience
International Conference on Computational Linguistics and Intelligent Systems (CoLInS)	April 2025, April 2026	Kharkiv-Kyiv, Ukraine	Academic
International Conference on Internet of Things, Big Data and Security (IoTBDs)	April 2025	Porto, Portugal	Academic
IEEE SmartComp 2025	June 2025	Cork, Ireland	Academic
Nordic Conference on Secure IT Systems (NordSec)	November 2025	Tartu, Estonia	Academic
Information Technology and Implementation	November 2025, November 2026	Kyiv, Ukraine	Academic

6.3 Open access publications in scientific journals

As part of its commitment to open-access dissemination, the TELEMETRY project aims to publish its research findings in high-impact scientific journals covering topics relevant to the project's scope. These publications will ensure that TELEMETRY's methodologies, advancements, and outcomes reach a broad academic and professional audience, fostering further research, collaboration, and industry adoption.

The following table (Table 9) is an indicative list of scientific journals where TELEMETRY partners plan to submit papers.

Table 9: Indicative scientific journals

Scientific journal	Link (publisher)	Partner(s) Involved
Computers and security	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computers-and-security	UoS
System research and information technologies	http://journal.iasa.kpi.ua/	WRCVE
Problems of Control and Informatics	https://www.begellhouse.com/journals/automation-and-information-sciences.html	WRCVE
Mathematical Modeling and Computing	https://science.lpnu.ua/mmc	WRCVE
International Scientific Technical	https://jais.net.ua	WRCVE
Computer Science	https://link.springer.com/journal/42979	UoS, SINTEF, Nokia, Antonov, TIM, WRCVE, ATC, i4RI, MTU & KUL
Discover Internet of Things	https://link.springer.com/journal/43926	MTU

6.4 Student conferences

The TELEMETRY project remains dedicated to engaging with young researchers and students by actively participating in student conferences to share knowledge, present research findings, and inspire future contributions to the field. This is an ongoing effort that will continue throughout the next 18 months, reinforcing TELEMETRY's commitment to fostering academic exchange and collaboration within the student and early-career research community.

Among the student conferences in which TELEMETRY will be represented is the II (VIII) International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists, titled "Information Technologies: Theory and Practice", taking place on April 2–4, 2025, in Zaporizhzhia-Kharkiv-Dnipro, Ukraine. Participation in such events allows the project to disseminate its research findings, engage with emerging talent, and encourage discussion on relevant topics related to TELEMETRY's objectives. More student-focused conferences and

academic initiatives will be pursued as the project progresses, ensuring a lasting academic impact and knowledge transfer.

6.5 Partner's networks

As highlighted in subsection 3.7, TELEMETRY partners have access to a broad and well-established network, providing valuable opportunities to disseminate project developments and results to key stakeholders. This extensive network enables the project to reach diverse audiences and relevant initiatives, ensuring that TELEMETRY's findings have a meaningful impact across multiple sectors.

In the upcoming period, TELEMETRY partners will continue to actively leverage these connections, integrating dissemination efforts into their existing collaborations, events, and professional engagements. By doing so, the project will enhance its outreach, foster cross-sector synergies, and facilitate the adoption of its outcomes.

Table 10 provides a summary of planned dissemination actions, outlining how TELEMETRY partners will utilise their networks to enhance visibility, share knowledge, and promote project results in the next phase of implementation.

Table 10: List of potential actions with partner's networks

Partner	Expected actions
Nokia	NOKIA will communicate about the TELEMETRY project in his partner networks (e.g. NESSI and BDVA) and as well Nokia internally towards its business units to communicate the technological achievements of TELEMETRY.
SINTEF	SINTEF will continue to communicate TELEMETRY results in Norwegian stakeholder forums and will explore possibilities to exploit our contacts in BDVA and AIOTI for increased reach within Europe.
MTU	MTU will continue to communicate about TELEMETRY in its partner network as was done in the previous reporting period. Suitable events and meetings within the partner network will be identified to reach a relevant target audience.
i4RI	Like in the previous period, i4RI will continue spreading the word of TELEMETRY within their partner's network. Co-location with other conferences is desirable to reach a wider audience.
ATC	ATC is planning to disseminate the results of the TELEMETRY project once they are finalised, ensuring they reach customers, partners, initiatives, and relevant associations. A key focus will be on engaging our customer base, leveraging the involvement of other business units within ATC's broader

	network. This approach aims to facilitate the implementation of TELEMETRY's outcomes across various vertical sectors, including health, manufacturing, and the public sector.
KU Leuven	KUL will continue to disseminate our work to the KUL industry network and the Belgium's Cyber Security Coalition
Telecom Italia	TIM will disseminate the results of the project, in particular the results related to the vulnerability discovery and testing procedures and methods to its internal engineering and operational departments concerned with the management of the Telecom Italia infrastructures and devices. Moreover, whenever relevant for the international and standardisation groups, the results will be presented and discussed.
Engineering	ENG collaborates with ECSO to actively contribute to the European cybersecurity ecosystem, participating in working groups, strategic discussions, and EU policy alignment. As part of this collaboration, ENG is co-organizing an online workshop in May 2025, bringing together CS-01-02 funded projects, including TELEMETRY, to present exploitation strategies. The selection criteria for featured projects are currently being defined. This synergy with ECSO enhances knowledge sharing, fosters partnerships, and supports the development of a resilient European cybersecurity landscape, while also facilitating funding opportunities, best practice exchange, and the promotion of research exploitation activities.
WRCVE	WRCVE plans to disseminate the positive experience of the project results, including access control systems effectiveness assessment, both among industrial enterprises responsible for critical infrastructure and in the academic environment. The goal is to improve the cybersecurity of information objects and exchange knowledge with interested specialists in these industries. At this stage, work was carried out to establish information interaction with key ministries of Ukraine (Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, Ministry for Strategic Industries of Ukraine, National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine) responsible for information policy in the field of information security, and the relevant letters of support for the TELEMETRY project were received.
Antonov	Antonov aims to share the project's successful outcomes, including the cargo monitoring system and aspects related to cybersecurity and IoT security and use these results in further AN-124 retrofit program (Avionics upgrading program in particularly flight monitoring system). In collaboration with the National Aviation University, Antonov is organizing a workshop under the <i>3rd International Workshop on Advances in Civil Aviation Systems Development</i> (March 19, 2025).
UOS	UoS is aiming to find a community around semi-automated risk assessment & management in complex socio-technical systems (e.g. cybersecurity, privacy, AI trustworthiness and specialist areas like medical devices, etc.). Its purpose is to bring together researchers, developers, experts,

practitioners, regulators, etc. in risk management by developing strategy, undertaking collaborative applied research and engaging with adopters for beneficial impact. The current status is early development and UoS is in talks with other organisations (notably SINTEF) to determine the Terms of Reference and plan of action for such a community.

6.6 Clustering (Liaison) activities with other EU projects

Collaboration with EU-funded projects remains a key element of TELEMETRY’s dissemination and impact strategy. As mentioned in Subsection 3.8, several projects have already been approached, and these partnerships will continue to be a cornerstone of TELEMETRY’s clustering activities. These efforts aim to foster knowledge exchange, enhance technological synergies, and amplify the impact of research findings. Through joint research initiatives, collaborative knowledge-sharing, and strategic networking, TELEMETRY ensures that its outcomes contribute meaningfully to the broader European research and innovation ecosystem.

As mentioned before, TELEMETRY has formally joined the European Clustering for Cybersecurity Certification, a cluster that fosters cooperation among projects focused on Next-Generation Agile Certification. One of the upcoming key activities within this cluster is the organization of a panel at the CLOSER 2025 Conference, scheduled to take place in Porto from April 1-3, 2025. If accepted, this panel will serve as a kick-off event for the cluster, setting the stage for deeper collaboration among participating projects.

In addition to this, TELEMETRY through its participation in the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI) will engage in joint scientific publications, co-organized events, and strategic discussions.

Table 11 provides an overview of the EU projects with which TELEMETRY has already established connections, identifying potential areas for collaboration. However, these efforts are ongoing, and additional projects may be approached as the initiative progresses, with all TELEMETRY partners expected to contribute to clustering activities.

Table 11: Indicative list of other EU projects for potential synergies

Project name	Acronym	Number	Expected areas of collaboration
Evidence Management for Continuous Certification as a Service in the Cloud	EMERALD	101120688	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testing each other’s tools • TELEMETRY tools as source of vulnerabilities for EMERALD

Agile conformance assessment for cybersecurity CERTIFICATION enhanced by Artificial Intelligence	CERTIFAI	101120606	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration on sharing knowledge, and joint actions on dissemination events through Panels, Workshops and/or Conferences
Cybersecurity for AI-augmented Systems	SEC4AI4SEC	101120393	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration on sharing knowledge, tools and technologies • Collaboration through Panels, Workshops and/or Conferences
Secure-by-Design IoT Operation with Supply Chain Control	DOSS	101120270	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the LIFESEC workshop during the SmartComp 2025 conference • Participation in a webinar for the IoTDay (April 9th)

6.7 Synergies with EU initiatives

While continuing the synergies established in Subsection 3.9, TELEMETRY aims to further expand its collaborations with EU initiatives to strengthen its impact and foster long-term engagement.

These initiatives present valuable opportunities for cooperation in research, dissemination, policy alignment, and technological innovation, ensuring the sustainability and broader adoption of TELEMETRY's outcomes.

The following indicative list (Table 12) outlines potential EU initiatives for collaboration. Additionally, a separate section details the TELEMETRY consortium partners involved in these initiatives, demonstrating the connections and contributions of each partner to foster collaboration within the European research ecosystem.

Table 12: Indicative list of EU Initiatives for potential synergies with TELEMETRY

EU initiative	Partner(s) involved
AIOTI (Alliance for AI, IoT and Edge Continuum Innovation)	SINTEF
ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute)	TIM
Networked European Software and Services Initiative (NESSI)	UoS, ATC, SINTEF, NOKIA, MTU

BDVA (Big Data Value Association)	ATC, SINTEF, NOKIA, ENG
Industrial IoT Consortium	MTU
GSMA (Global System for Mobile communications Association)	TIM, NOKIA
EOS (European Organization for Security)	ENG
NGMN (Next Generation Mobile Network)	TIM, NOKIA

- **NESSI:** This initiative focuses on software and services in Europe. Multiple partners, including SINTEF, UoS, ATC, ENG, and Nokia, are involved, indicating a collaborative effort in advancing software and services innovation.
- **AIOTI:** SINTEF's involvement in AIOTI suggests a commitment to fostering IoT innovation and collaboration within Europe.
- **ETSI:** TIM's participation in ETSI highlights its role in developing globally applicable standards for Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), ensuring interoperability and fostering innovation.
- **Industrial IoT Consortium:** MTU's engagement indicates a focus on accelerating the growth of the Industrial Internet by identifying best practices, reference architectures, and frameworks.
- **GSMA:** With TIM and Nokia as members, this association underscores their involvement in uniting mobile operators and organizations to advance the mobile ecosystem.
- **European Organization for Security (EOS):** ENG's participation reflects a dedication to enhancing Europe's security capabilities through collaborative efforts.
- **Next Generation Mobile Network (NGMN):** The involvement of TIM and Nokia signifies their commitment to the development of next-generation mobile broadband networks.

6.8 Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms

As mentioned in Subsection 3.10, several EU initiatives have been identified and engaged by TELEMETRY over the past months, with many of these remaining a focus for collaboration in the upcoming period. While UOS, KUL, and WRCVE have been primarily involved in establishing these connections, all TELEMETRY partners are expected to contribute to strengthening and expanding these synergies.

Although ongoing collaboration is encouraged, these initiatives often operate on their own schedules, requiring a proactive approach to engagement. To ensure effective participation,

relevant events and opportunities from these initiatives will be communicated to the entire TELEMETRY consortium in advance, allowing sufficient time for preparation and coordination.

Table 13 provides an overview of the EU initiatives that TELEMETRY has already identified for future engagement. However, additional initiatives may be approached and integrated into the project’s dissemination and collaboration strategy as new opportunities arise.

Table 13: Indicative list of National or Regional Initiatives for potential synergies with TELEMETRY

National or regional initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) involved
NCSC	Continue engagement	UoS
IIoT-SBOM	This initiative is closed	KUL
NSAI	MTU is represented on several national mirror committees for ISO standards including Blockchain, Energy Management and Industrial Automation. Alan McGibney is national expert representative for the Blockchain Interoperability WG	MTU
Cyber Ireland	Leading partner	MTU
IDSA	MTU is a member of the Architecture Working Group	MTU
Computer Emergency Response Team of Ukraine	To combine efforts and to support the implementation of results and methodologies from TELEMETRY	WRCVE
Scientific Cyber Security Association of Ukraine	To combine efforts and to support the implementation of results and methodologies from TELEMETRY	WRCVE

6.9 Training – demos

As part of its commitment to knowledge transfer and capacity building, TELEMETRY will organise training sessions and demonstrations to equip technicians, laboratories, and technical staff with the skills to deploy and utilize its tools and methodologies. These activities will ensure the seamless integration of TELEMETRY’s innovations into operational workflows, enhancing cybersecurity resilience. In the second half of the project, training efforts will intensify, focusing on practical deployment, hands-on demonstrations, and interactive workshops to facilitate effective adoption and application across industries.

In detail, Nokia will provide comprehensive training on Smart Manufacturing and TELEMETRY Tools. As we advance into the second half of our project, Nokia is dedicated to onboarding

new colleagues, including those from start-ups like Botcraft, through detailed training on use case 2 (Smart Manufacturing) and TELEMETRY tools. This training will cover the TELEMETRY architecture, Nokia's tools, their roles in the project, and the source code.

The program will provide insights into the TELEMETRY architecture. Participants will learn about Nokia's tools for detecting network and production anomalies, identifying vulnerabilities, and supporting operators in implementing countermeasures.

A hands-on approach will be taken to explore the source code, enabling trainees to understand its structure, troubleshooting issues, and optimize performance. The training will also emphasise early detection and prevention of cyber-attacks, teaching participants to monitor network activity and respond to threats promptly.

TIM is planning an upgrade to the current lab environment to provide TELEMETRY tool owners with a more effective and flexible testbed for developing and testing their tools. This upgrade will involve deploying a completely new infrastructure, with lab facilities accessed through a dedicated client. To ensure tool owners can fully take advantage of the new environment, TIM will provide a specialized training session to the tools owners involved in the TELEMETRY project. This session will demonstrate the capabilities and the potential of the upgraded lab, focusing on key features such as creating and managing virtual machines, adjusting the network LAN configuration within the implemented scenarios, intercepting traffic across different network segments, and more.

ANTONOV is planning to provide full access to the bench test in Leipzig with wired approach and as a next step of this is to provide full access to the bench test in Kyiv with WLAN approach with IoT sensors for all partners or developing and testing their tools. As a demonstration of the results of remote evaluation and testing cargo monitoring system can be installed on the aircraft An-124 with all necessary tools for flight testing. The results of flight testing will be presented to Antonov's customers (Bolloré, Airbus, TAI (Turkish aerospace industry)). Antonov will focus on practical deployment, hands-on demonstrations, and interactive workshops to facilitate effective adoption and application of the practical results of TELEMETRY program across other projects as a part of An-124 retrofit program. The audience is employees of Antonov Company and Antonov's partners in air transportation area and avionics, students of National Aviation University

In accordance with the requirements and recommendations of ICAO, EASA and the State Aviation Administration of Ukraine, airlines must have a fully functioning flight safety management system (the requirements for the system are set out in Annex 19 of the Chicago Convention and in the Flight Safety Management Manual Doc. 9859), the full functioning of the SMS requires a system for identifying hazardous factors, which is based on a reactive, proactive and predictive method, as well as a risk assessment system. TELEMETRY tools can be used in the development of such a system at Antonov.

6.10 Workshops and demonstrations

In the upcoming months and until the end of the project, TELEMETRY will continue to organise and participate in workshops and demonstrations, ensuring the practical application and dissemination of its tools and methodologies. These activities will involve contributions from all project partners.

One of the confirmed events is the LIFESEC workshop, scheduled for 16th June 2025, where TELEMETRY will present its advancements and foster discussions on whole-lifecycle security for smart systems. In addition to this, several other workshops and demonstrations are already planned, with more to be developed as the project progresses. The list of planned activities is not exhaustive, and further initiatives will be introduced to ensure TELEMETRY's continued engagement with stakeholders and industry professionals.

Nokia will present the achievements of TELEMETRY to research groups in Bell Labs and the operations department of the business unit Cloud and Network Services. These presentations will highlight the significant advancements and practical applications of TELEMETRY within the context of Smart Manufacturing. The focus will be on the specific use cases that have been successfully implemented, showcasing how TELEMETRY tools have been utilized to enhance network monitoring, detect anomalies, and support operational efficiency.

Additionally, the presentations will delve into the various tools involved in the TELEMETRY system, providing detailed insights into their functionalities and contributions to the project's success. The technological achievements will be a key highlight, demonstrating the innovative solutions developed by the TELEMETRY project. By sharing these accomplishments, Nokia aims to foster collaboration and inspire further research.

TIM, owner of the UC3, the Telco Use case, is planning a series of demonstrations to be shown during the first technical review scheduled at the beginning of April 2025. Depending on the maturity of the tools developed, these demonstrations will showcase the capabilities of deployed security testing tools in addressing key challenges faced by security testers when evaluating Residential Gateway (RGW) devices. Particular attention will be put on identification of zero-day vulnerabilities, vulnerability prioritization and supply chain risks. The demonstrations will be conducted on real devices to provide a practical understanding of the TELEMETRY tools and their impact on existing security testing procedures.

In the coming period, ENG will provide training material for pilots' personnel on the implementation and use of BACON within the TELEMETRY project. The material, after appropriate refinement, could be used for exercises or cybersecurity training of TELEMETRY external stakeholders.

Among the workshops and training sessions planned, WRCVE will organise two events in 2025:

- (VIII) International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists "Information Technologies: Theory and Practice" (April 2-4, 2025), providing a platform for young researchers to discuss advancements in information technologies and their practical applications.
- The Twenty-Seven International Scientific and Practical Seminar "Combinatorial Configurations and Their Applications" (June 4-6, 2025), focusing on combinatorial mathematics and its real-world applications.

These workshops will contribute to TELEMETRY's dissemination and knowledge-sharing efforts, engaging students, researchers, and industry professionals in discussions relevant to the project's objectives.

In addition to the planned workshops and demonstrations, several TELEMETRY partners will actively support and contribute to these activities without directly hosting their own events. i4RI will participate in TELEMETRY-organised events, where its activities related to the Misuse Detection Toolkit will be broadcasted, and demonstrated to the audience. Similarly, KUL will join and support project-led initiatives, contributing its expertise to relevant events. While KUL is not developing a tool for standalone demonstration, it will provide a cryptographic library for other partners to integrate, which may be showcased as part of their tools during demonstrations. Through these contributions, both partners will play a crucial role in expanding TELEMETRY's outreach and ensuring the adoption and visibility of its technologies.

Additionally, MTU and SINTEF will provide their assistance in the actions planned by the consortium and are in the process of planning workshops to be conducted. Both partners are playing an active role in the LIFESEC workshop, further strengthening TELEMETRY's engagement and impact within the cybersecurity communities.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable, D5.5 “*Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities*”, provides a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication efforts carried out during the first 18 months of the TELEMETRY project and outlines the future plans for the remaining duration. The report highlights the strategic approach implemented to enhance TELEMETRY’s visibility, engage key stakeholders, and ensure the effective dissemination of project outcomes across multiple channels and target groups; the deliverable also reports on the consortium’s activities that took place during the 1st Reporting Period (M1 – M18) and on achievements on requested KPIs.

Throughout this period, TELEMETRY has successfully established its branding and communication infrastructure, including the project website, social media channels, newsletters, press releases, and promotional materials. The project has actively participated in scientific conferences, clustering activities, and EU-wide initiatives, reinforcing its position. These efforts will be complemented by the planned development of project videos, podcasts, and targeted dissemination materials, which aim to further enhance engagement with relevant audiences and broaden the project’s outreach in the coming months.

Looking ahead, TELEMETRY will expand and refine its dissemination and communication activities to amplify its impact and reach. The project will continue to update and enhance its website, integrating details on tools and use cases, while leveraging its social media presence, newsletters, and press releases to share key developments. A particular emphasis will be placed on scientific publications, participation in major conferences, and collaboration with EU-funded initiatives to foster knowledge exchange and cross-sector synergies.

Furthermore, TELEMETRY will intensify its efforts in workshops and demonstrations, ensuring the practical application and adoption of its tools and methodologies. Several training activities are planned to equip technicians, labs, and stakeholders with the necessary expertise to implement TELEMETRY’s innovations effectively. Additionally, partners will continue to contribute to EU-wide clustering efforts, engaging in joint research, exploitation strategies, and collaborative initiatives to enhance the long-term sustainability of TELEMETRY’s results.

By maintaining an adaptive and multi-channel dissemination strategy, TELEMETRY ensures that its findings, tools, and methodologies will continue to generate value beyond the project’s lifecycle. The activities outlined in this deliverable will serve as the foundation for ongoing outreach, impact assessment, and stakeholder engagement, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and secure IoT ecosystem across Europe.

8 Annexes

8.1 Annex I: Newsletters and press releases

8.1.1 Newsletters

Figure 32: TELEMETRY second newsletter

Figure 33: TELEMETRY first newsletter

8.1.2 Press releases

Press Release

Wednesday, 28th May 2024

Project Coordinator contact:

Mr. Robert Seidl, (info[at]telemetry-project[dot]eu), Research Manager at Nokia Bell Labs
For further information visit <https://telemetry-project.eu/>.

TELEMETRY: Enhancing Cybersecurity in IoT Ecosystems with Trustworthy Tools and Methodologies

The TELEMETRY project, a European Union's Horizon Europe initiative, is set to revolutionize the security landscape of IoT devices and systems. This ambitious project aims to develop and validate innovative and trustworthy tools and methods for testing and detecting security vulnerabilities in IoT environments. The project will conduct three pilot programs in the telecoms, aerospace, and manufacturing sectors, ensuring broad applicability and impact. These pilots will showcase improvements in threat and vulnerability detection accuracy, response time, and the cost of testing and verification.

Specifically, the TELEMETRY project aims to support the creation and sustainability of resilient digital infrastructures, systems, and processes through continuous vulnerability and risk analysis of IoT components and ecosystems. The project addresses all aspects of the IoT lifecycle, from development and integration to operation by providing trustworthy tools for continuous assessment of heterogeneous, interlinked components and systems.

In fact, TELEMETRY outlines five specific objectives to ensure its long-term impact: a) establishing holistic testing methodologies and integrating tools into a comprehensive toolkit, b) providing tools for vulnerability detection and secure updates, c) managing cyber threat intelligence and risk, and d) grounding the project's innovations in real-world IoT ecosystems.

Within this spectrum, the project team creates advanced methods for identifying and mitigating security vulnerabilities in IoT devices, such as machine-learning models and algorithms for real-time anomaly detection, dynamic risk assessment to simulate threat consequences, reputation management, and privacy-preserving data sharing. Additionally, TELEMETRY includes an IoT device emulation and analysis environment and lightweight

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Press Release

Figure 34: TELEMETRY first press release (1st page)

approaches for trusted updates. These advancements will promote continuous improvement and assurance across both design and runtime phases.

Last but not least, TELEMETRY project fosters collaboration, by involving leading experts from academia, research institutions, and innovative private companies in the ICT, telecoms, aviation, manufacturing and consulting industries. These are Nokia Solutions and Networks GmbH & Co. KG in Germany, SINTEF AS in Norway, Munster Technological University in Ireland, Data Analytics for Industries 4.0 in Spain, Athens Technology Center in Greece, KU Leuven in Belgium, Telecom Italia S.p.A. in Italy, Engineering Ingegneria Informatica in Italy, World Research Center of Vortex Energy in Ukraine, ANTONOV Company in Ukraine, and the University of Southampton in the UK.

Mr. Robert Seidl, Research Manager at Nokia Bell Labs, expressed his belief that through collaboration, innovation, and rigorous testing, the project will deliver tools that enhance security across various industries, benefiting businesses and citizens alike and also stressed the importance of EU investment in IoT security: *"The TELEMETRY consortium is dedicated to developing reliable tools, techniques, and holistic methodologies for cybersecurity testing and vulnerability detection at both component and system levels. Led by Nokia, TELEMETRY will showcase these advancements through three real-world use cases in aviation, smart manufacturing, and telecommunications."*

The shift towards license-free open-source code, cloud services, and distributed open networks highlights the importance of TELEMETRY's tools and techniques for managing complex systems. This project emphasizes the consortium's commitment to enhancing cybersecurity across diverse industrial sectors".

The TELEMETRY project held its kick-off meeting in Munich from September 12-14, 2023, hosted by NOKIA. This initial gathering set the stage for collaboration and outlined the project's roadmap. The following key event was the project plenary meeting held in Rome from March 12-14, 2024, hosted by Engineering, where significant progress and future steps were discussed. During this meeting, we aligned on the architecture and finalized tool descriptions for use across different cases, setting a clear direction for future development.

Disclaimer:

The project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101119747. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author (s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 35: TELEMETRY first press release (2nd page)

Press Release

Friday, 24th January 2025

Project Coordinator contact:

Mr. Robert Seidl, (info[at]telemetry-project[dot]eu), Research Manager at Nokia Bell Labs

For further information visit <https://telemetry-project.eu/>.

SmartComp 2025: TELEMETRY Project announces Workshop on Whole Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems (LIFESEC)

The TELEMETRY project is pleased to announce the **Workshop on Whole Lifecycle Security for Smart Systems: Methods and Tools (LIFESEC)**, hosted as part of the IEEE International Conference on Smart Computing (SmartComp 2025). The conference will take place from 16 to 19 June 2025 in Cork, Ireland, with the LIFESEC workshop scheduled for 16 June 2025. This workshop is jointly organised by the Horizon Europe projects TELEMETRY and DOSS, bringing together experts to explore innovative solutions for lifecycle security in smart systems.

This workshop aims to bring together researchers, developers, and professionals to address one of the most pressing challenges in today's connected world: achieving comprehensive security across the entire lifecycle of smart systems.

Within this spectrum, the Call for Papers is now open, inviting innovative contributions that explore groundbreaking methods, tools, and strategies for lifecycle security in smart systems. Researchers and practitioners are encouraged to submit their work by 30 March 2025. Selected papers will be presented during the workshop, providing an opportunity to share ideas, gain feedback, and engage with leading experts and practitioners.

Call for Papers: Topics of interest

The workshop welcomes submissions in the following broad areas:

- Lifecycle Security and Risk Management
- Tools and Technologies for Cybersecurity
- Regulation and Compliance
- Secure Systems Design and Operation
- Digital Twins and Holistic Methodologies

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Press Release

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Figure 36: TELEMETRY second press release (1st page)

- Automation and Intelligence in Cybersecurity

Also, papers addressing the holistic topic of security across the entire lifecycle of smart systems will be considered.

Workshop organisers

The workshop is organised and guided by its co-chairs, Mr Robert Seidl (NOKIA, Germany), Dr. Bernd-Ludwig Wenning (Munster Technological University, Ireland), and Prof. Antonio Skarmeta (University of Murcia, Spain), whose expertise ensures a high-quality program fostering meaningful discussions and innovative ideas. A Technical Program Committee will review submitted papers, ensuring the selection of impactful contributions that advance lifecycle security for smart systems (visit the official event page for details).

Workshop highlights

Participants in the LIFESEC Workshop will benefit from an engaging program that includes keynote talks by world-class experts in smart system security, offering insights into the latest advancements and trends in the field. Interactive panel discussions will delve into emerging challenges and solutions, fostering dynamic exchanges of ideas. Additionally, the workshop offers unparalleled opportunities to collaborate with a global network of researchers and industry professionals, creating a vibrant platform for innovation and partnership.

Who should attend?

The workshop is ideal for researchers, engineers, developers, and anyone passionate about building secure, sustainable, and resilient smart systems. Whether you are in academia, industry, or government, this event provides the platform to stay ahead of emerging threats and best practices.

Register and submit your paper today

Participation in the workshop is part of SmartComp 2025, and registration is required. Don't miss the chance to contribute to this cutting-edge discussion on lifecycle security for smart systems.

For further details about the workshop and the Call for Papers, [visit the official event page](#)

About the TELEMETRY Project

The [TELEMETRY project](#) is a European Union-funded initiative dedicated to advancing security and trust in smart systems. By connecting researchers and practitioners, it drives innovation and fosters the creation of resilient, secure technologies for the future.

Media contact:

Spyridoula Markou
Communication & Dissemination Manager
info[at]telemetry-project[dot]eu

Disclaimer:

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Figure 37: TELEMETRY second press release (2nd page)

8.2 Annex II: Partners presentations

8.2.1 “SBOM – Sovemedicin eller eksplosivt virkermiddel?”

SBOM Generator

- The SBOM (software bill of materials) generator gives an overview of the software components and libraries included in a software product. This will in turn allow the tool to list known vulnerabilities present in the software product and the vulnerabilities' severity.

Foiler fra Ravi Borgaonkar, SINTEF

Figure 38: Slide from the presentation titled “SBOM – Sovemedicin eller eksplosivt virkermiddel?” by Martin Gilje Jaatun (SINTEF)

Spørsmål?

 TELEMETRY

<https://telemetry-project.eu/>

 SINTEF

Teknologi for et bedre samfunn

<https://infosec.sintef.no>

Martin.G.Jaatun@sintef.no

 @seniorfrosk@snabelen.no

Figure 39: Slide from the presentation titled “SBOM – Sovemedisin eller eksplosivt virkemedel?” by Martin Gilje Jaatun (SINTEF)